

STUDIES IN COLLOIDAL ARSENIC TRISULPHIDE. PART I. DIALYSIS AND ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY OF THE SOL

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On dialysis of colloidal arsenic trisulphide, the dialysate shows the presence of arsenious acid and sulphuric acid. The equivalent conductivity of the micelles does not show the behaviour of a typical colloidal electrolyte but is greater than that of the gegenion, if existing in a free condition.

Colloidal arsenic trisulphide sol has been the subject of numerous investigations (Weiser, "Inorganic Colloid Chemistry", Vol. III, 1938, pp. 167-221). Dialysis and conductivity of the sol were studied by many workers (Pauli and Semler, *Kolloid Z.*, 1924, 34, 145; Desai and Barve, *Trans. Nat. Inst. Sci. India*, 1939, 2, No. 2, 39; Murphy and Mathews, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 45, 16; Rabinovitch and Dorfmann, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1928, 131, 313; Mankodi *et al.*, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1930, 5, Pt. 2, 53; Joshi *et al.*, *Curr. Sci.*, 1934, 3, 105; Jha and Ghosh, this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 270). The properties of the sol have been interpreted with respect to hydrogen sulphide as a stabilising electrolyte.

In the case of aged arsenic trisulphide sol, on the other hand, Kargin and Klimovitzkaja (*J. Phys. Chem., U. S. S. R.*, 1934, 5, 969) observed that arsenious acid rather than hydrogen sulphide was the stabilising electrolyte. Kharin (*Kolloid-Zhur*, 1943, 10, 159) pointed out that aged arsenic trisulphide sols contained sulphuric acid in the intermicellar liquid. In the light of this information, the dialysis and the conductivity of the sol have been reinvestigated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Concentrated arsenic trisulphide sols were prepared by passing H_2S into a clear, saturated solution of arsenious acid at room temperature till no free arsenious acid was present. The sols were concentrated by slow evaporation on a water-bath.

The sol was analysed as before for the colloid and arsenious acid contents (Trivedi and Patani, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 683) and sulphuric acid was determined as barium sulphate. The sol used for dialysis contained 60.1 g./litre of As_2S_3 and 33 and 2.1 m. e./litre of arsenious acid and sulphuric acid respectively.

The dialysis of colloidal arsenic trisulphide was carried out in a parchment paper bag, in cold, by adding sodium chloride as a reference substance. Chloride and arsenious acid contents in the dialysate were analysed from time to time. Initially, the dialysate was slightly yellow but contained very little arsenic trisulphide, which was neglected. After one or two changes of water, the dialysate was almost clear. The dialysis at higher temperatures was followed by analysing the dialysate for arsenious acid and sulphuric acid.

The conductivity of the sols was determined by using a Leeds and Northrup conductivity assembly. In the case of the two sols, A and B, conductivity was determined at different dilutions, the dilutions being performed after Trivedi, Divatia and Patani (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1952, **36A**, 530). In measuring the conductivity of arsenic trisulphide sol, particularly on dilution, an interesting observation was made. There was a perceptible change of conductivity with time. This cannot be attributed to the liberation of the gegenions from the micelles as the change is fairly rapid. This phenomenon is unique in the sense that it has not been noticed in the case of sulphur sol (Bolam and Trivedi, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1943, **39**, 247), iron oxide sol (Trivedi, Divatia and Patani, *loc. cit.*) and chromium oxide sol (Trivedi, Bhattacharya and Divatia, unpublished work). Hence, it was found necessary to take the readings as rapidly as possible.

Table I records the concentrations of the different constituents together with the data on conductivity of the sols under investigation.

TABLE I

Sol. No.	Colloid content (g./litre).	As ₂ O ₃ (m.e./litre).	H ₂ SO ₄ (m.e./litre).	Specific conductivity of		
				the sol. (K × 10 ³).	H ₂ SO ₄ (K' × 10 ³).	the micelles [(K - K') × 10 ³].
A	155.0	42	4.5	2.8	1.9	0.9
B	124.9	35	3.4	2.2	1.5	0.7
C	130.5	40	3.1	2.3	1.3	1.0
D	130.5	40	3.2	2.4	1.4	1.0

DISCUSSION

The results of dialysis in cold show that while the amount of chloride added as a reference substance is gradually reduced to a negligible proportion, the amount of arsenious acid remains practically constant. Arsenious acid is being continuously formed in the sol according to the equation

This has been known for a long time (Weiser, *loc. cit.*). A part of hydrogen sulphide is converted into sulphuric acid, as first pointed out by Kharin (*loc. cit.*). Dialysis at a higher temperature has been found to increase the rates of formation of both As₂O₃ and H₂SO₄.

Arsenious acid is a very weak electrolyte, while sulphuric acid is a strong one. The formation of sulphuric acid throws light on the results of dialysis of the sol obtained by previous workers. Pauli and Semler (*loc. cit.*) dialysed the sol continuously and followed the changes on dialysis by measuring the conductivity of the sol from time to time, and found an initial sharp decrease in conductivity followed by a slow increase. As the work of Kharin (*loc. cit.*) as well as of ours shows, the sol investigated by Pauli might initially contain some sulphuric acid

depending upon the previous history of the sol, particularly whether it was kept in darkness or partly exposed to light. The initial sharp decrease in conductivity may be attributed to the removal of sulphuric acid by dialysis. The subsequent increase of conductivity suggests that the formation of sulphuric acid is more rapid than its removal on dialysis. Desai and Barve (*loc. cit.*) reported the decrease in conductivity, followed by an increase, and succeeded by a decrease. The first two points can be easily explained on the lines indicated above. The last one may be explained, following Desai and Barve, as due to "desorption of the primarily adsorbed ions". It is important to point out that both Pauli and Semler's experiments, as well as of Desai and Barve require that the rate of dialysis throughout must remain constant, a condition which is not easy to establish experimentally.

TABLE II

Sol A.			Sol B.		
Conc. of the sol.	$K \times 10^3$.	$(K/c) \times 10^5$.	Conc. of the sol.	$K \times 10^3$.	$(K/c) \times 10^5$.
100 %	2.8	2.8	100 %	2.2	2.2
90	2.6	2.9	75	1.7	2.3
80	2.3	2.9	50	1.1	2.2
70	2.0	2.9	25	0.58	2.3
60	1.7	2.8	10	0.25	2.5
50	1.4	2.8	5	0.13	2.6
40	1.1	2.8	2	0.06	3.0
30	0.85	2.9			
20	0.57	2.9			
10	0.30	3.0			

Table II records the values of the specific conductivity, K and K/c at different dilutions in the case of sols A and B. The original sols are taken as 100%. By analogy with sulphur, iron oxide and chromium oxide sols (*loc. cit.*) it was expected that the colloidal arsenic trisulphide might also exhibit the behaviour of a typical colloidal electrolyte, in the sense that the equivalent conductivity due to the micelles should decrease and then increase with dilution. The absence of this behaviour is probably connected with the formation of sulphuric acid which masks the actual variation of conductivity due to the micelles on dilution.

The results obtained become interesting when we consider the conductivity of the concentrated sols. The sols contain, besides the micelles, sulphuric acid and arsenious acid. The conductivity of arsenious acid is negligible (Zawidzki, *Ber.*, 1903, 36, 1429). The specific conductivities of sulphuric acid solutions at various concentrations were read from a prepared graph of equivalent conductivity against concentration (c), the necessary data being obtained from the Handbook of Chemistry and Physics (Chemical Rubber Publishing Co., 29th Ed., 1945, pp. 1920, 1923). The specific conductivity due to the micelles is obtained by deducting the specific conductivity of sulphuric acid from that of the sol.

The data concerning the specific conductivity due to the micelles are shown in Table I. These values are subject to an error of about 10-20%. Taking the lowest

value of the specific conductivity due to the micelles and allowing for 20% error, the equivalent conductivity due to the micelles will be

$$\frac{1000 \times (0.7 \times 10^{-3}) \times 0.80}{0.035} = 16.0 \text{ ohms}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2.$$

The equivalent conductivity of free arsenious acid varies from 0.22/2 to 2.11/2 (Zawidzky, *loc. cit.*). Thus, the adsorbed arsenious acid appears to have a much greater equivalent conductivity than free arsenious acid. An alternative explanation would be, that the sol may contain an additional electrolyte, say polythionic acid. But polythionate was found absent, as further supported by Kharin (*loc. cit.*). The presence of any other electrolyte, besides sulphuric acid and arsenious acid, may be also ruled out by the data on ageing of arsenic trisulphide sol (Part II, this issue, p. 13).

Hence, one is left with a conclusion that when a weak electrolyte like arsenious acid is adsorbed by the colloidal As_2S_3 , its conductivity, and therefore its dissociation, actually increases. Adsorption on a colloidal particle in the case of a weak electrolyte promotes ionisation.

The conclusion is rather surprising, but does not seem improbable (cf. Weiser, *loc. cit.*, Vol. II, 1938, p. 108). Jacques Gilbert's observation (*Compt. rend.*, 1952, 284, 1916), that the conductivity due to the micelles in the case of arsenic trisulphide sol is considerably more than that can be accounted for by the conductivity of the original constituents or of the products of aerial oxidation, supports a similar view.

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